

UNVEILING THE LINGUISTIC TAPESTRY: EXPLORING
ONOMASTICS AND PROPER NAMES

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Abstract:

This study delves into the multifaceted domain of onomastics, a linguistic discipline dedicated to the study of proper names within language systems. It explores the unique features and characteristics of proper names, investigating their nomination, origins, and role within the broader lexicon. The research aims to elucidate the influence of extralinguistic factors on the formation and evolution of proper names, contributing to their codification, regulation, and lexicography. Through an analysis of various onomastic sources such as geographical maps, historical essays, and archival documents, this study sheds light on the intricate nature of proper names and their significance within linguistic studies. By examining the structural, phonetic-phonological, and morphological aspects of proper names, as well as their etymology and semantic nuances, this research provides valuable insights into the complex world of onomastics. Ultimately, this study serves as a comprehensive exploration of proper names, highlighting their diverse facets and contributions to linguistic research.

Key words: onomastics, proper names, linguistic discipline, lexical categories, nomination, origins, codification, lexicography, corpus, etymology, atlases, dictionaries.

Introduction:

Onomastics, as a linguistic discipline, is dedicated to the study of proper names (PN) and their role within language systems. Its pursuit encompasses a broad spectrum of goals aimed at unraveling the intricacies of proper names, particularly in relation to other layers of vocabulary. The overarching purpose of onomastic research is multifaceted. It seeks to delineate the specifics of proper names within the language system, identifying unique onomastic features that distinguish them from other lexical categories. Moreover, it delves into the study of various categories and classes of proper names, exploring their nomination and functional characteristics. Additionally, onomastics endeavors to ascertain the influence of extralinguistic factors on the formation of proper names, unraveling their origins, and contributing to the codification, regulation, and lexicography of proper names. To achieve these objectives, onomastic research is tasked with a range of specific goals. These include the determination and inventory of the proper name corpus, the comprehensive collection of factual material, the identification of structural and word-formation features specific to each category of proper names, and the elucidation of phonetic-phonological and morphological aspects. Furthermore, onomastics involves the etymological analysis of proper names, the creation of onomastic atlases and dictionaries, and the study of specialized onomastic sources such as geographical maps, historical essays, and archival documents. These sources provide invaluable insights into the nature and evolution of proper names. Overall, this chapter serves as an introduction to the origins of onomastics, highlights previous research endeavors, and elucidates the diverse facets of onomastic studies.

Main part. Onomastics - linguistic science Onomastics 'the art of giving names' is a branch of linguistics that studies proper names, which serve to individually designate any animate or inanimate object, phenomenon, event, period of time, etc. The term "onomastics" was also called the totality of proper names - onyms, referred to in modern science as "onymy". The register of proper names of

a certain people, a certain territory or text is denoted by the term "onomasticon" (cf. lexicon). In separate onomastic works until the 60s of the twentieth century. the term "onomastics" was used in the meaning of "anthroponymy", i.e. the totality of all the names that call a person.

In some works of Russian scientists of the mid-twentieth century, (A.A. Reformatsky and others) the term toponomastics is found to denote the science of geographical names. One of the conditions for the emergence and development of any science, in particular onomastics, is the availability of what needs to be studied, what research activities need to be directed to, i.e. the object of study should be identified. In the general paradigm of the disciplinary model of science, the object of scientific research is understood as objects, phenomena, processes of reality, with which the subjects of science interact in cognitive activity.

Based on this position, the object of onomastics is the proper names of all categories, both native and borrowed from other languages, constituting a kind of subsystem of the general lexical fund of the language. A proper name includes all words, phrases or sentences that serve to highlight the named object among other objects, its individualization and identification. All onyms are nouns; when they are formed from words of another part-of-speech affiliation, the unit is obligatory substantiated. Proper names are an onomastic universal, since no language, no culture can do without them. However, each nation has its own corpus of proper names (hereinafter referred to as IP), the volume and content of which depends on the degree of involvement and differentiation of objects of real and fictional reality in the nomination process.

Depending on the named object (name denotation), ISs are divided into different categories, which, in turn, on the basis of hyper-hyponymic relations, can be divided into separate classes (types) and subclasses (subtypes). So, for example, an anthroponym is a category of onyms that combines classes of names denoting a person or a group of people, including a personal name, patronymic, surname,

nickname, pseudonym, cryptonym (secret name), nickname, andronym (naming a wife by name, nickname or husband's surnames), gyneconym (name of a man by the name or nickname of his mother or wife, which can become a surname), patronym (name of a person formed from the name (nickname) of the father or paternal ancestors). Hyper-hyponymic relations can be clearly represented on the example of the names of the terrestrial space - toponyms² [see. Table 1]: Table 1. Proper names of the terrestrial space – toponyms

The subject of science in a general sense is what the subject is looking for in the object of study, the result of interaction (process, phenomenon), connection, relationship of natural and artificial origin. The subject of onomastics is the system of linguistic means used to form both natural and artificial IS, their structure, semantic and word-formation models, correlation of IS with each other, declension features, IS syntax, functions performed, etc. Like any other science that has its own object and subject of study, onomastics pursues its goals.

The purpose of onomastic research is to determine the specifics of IP in the language system, to identify specific onomastic features that affect the features of studying IP in relation to other layers of vocabulary, to study different categories and classes of onyms, to determine the onomastic nomination and functional features of IP. In addition, the goals of onomastics include determining the influence of extralinguistic factors on the formation of onyms, revealing the origin of IP, codification and regulation of IP, lexicography of IP, and many others. Based on certain goals, it is possible to identify the tasks of onomastic research:

- determination and inventory of the IP corpus required for study (based on the criteria for dividing onyms);
- complete (if possible) collection of factual material;
- identification of structural and word-formation features characteristic of each category of IS;

- elucidation of the phonetic-phonological and morphological features of IP;
- definition of semantics of proper names;
- etymological analysis of IP;
- creation of onomastic atlases and maps;
- creation of special onomastic dictionaries of various types;
- study of special onomastic sources, etc.

Special onomastic sources include geographical maps and atlases, travel notes, journalism, mass media, geographical and historical essays, written monuments, archival documents, reference indexes, telephone and address books, registration books, act documents, etc. – anything that can provide useful information about IP. Various types of onomastic (toponymic, anthroponymic, zoonymic, terminological, etc.) dictionaries can serve as independent sources of research.

All in all, this chapter provides information about the origin of onomastics, researches that was done before by scientists, various types of onomastics and their representations.

In conclusion, this thesis has provided a comprehensive examination of onomastics, highlighting its significance as a linguistic discipline and its role in unraveling the complexities of proper names within language systems. Through an exploration of various onomastic features, including nomination, origins, and structural characteristics, this study has contributed to a deeper understanding of the nature and evolution of proper names. The analysis of extralinguistic factors influencing proper name formation has shed light on the dynamic interplay between language and culture in shaping onyms. Furthermore, this research has underscored the importance of onomastics in codifying and regulating proper names, as well as its contributions to lexicography and etymological studies. By delving into specialized onomastic sources and employing diverse research

methodologies, this thesis has provided valuable insights into the diverse facets of proper names and their significance within linguistic studies. Moving forward, further research in onomastics promises to continue unraveling the mysteries of proper names, enriching our understanding of language and culture.

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